

MASTER PROJECT LAUNCHES 2ND OPEN CALL: UP TO €100,000 TO BRING YOUR EDUCATIONAL XR CONTENT TO LIFE

The MASTER project is excited to announce the launch of its 2nd Open Call, inviting educational institutions to shape the future of XR-based learning. Building on the success of the first call, the 2nd Open Call focuses on validating XR technologies within real educational settings and expanding the library of immersive learning content through the MASTER platform.

Open from 7 April to 12 June 2025, this call offers selected applicants financial support of up to €100,000, access to advanced XR tools, and tailored mentorship to design and test educational experiences that push the boundaries of traditional training methods

Eligible applicants for the 2nd Open Call include educational institutions that provide education and content creation services and can involve students in the testing of XR applications. The consortium must include at least one University/Research/Education non-profit organization, which must also serve as the coordinator. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) may participate in the Open Call as part of a consortium but are not eligible to apply independently. Large companies may also be involved, though only in the role of challenge providers. Applicants must be legally established in EU Member States, Overseas Countries and Territories (OCTs), or countries associated with Horizon Europe.

The 2nd Open Call represents a valuable opportunity to validate cutting-edge XR technologies in educational or professional training environments, develop innovative educational content to be integrated into the MASTER platform, and receive expert mentoring and support from the MASTER consortium throughout the process.

The Open Call has been published in the [MASTER portal](#) and in the [EU Commission Funding & Tenders Portal](#). In addition, the project website has a dedicated page for the Open Call, where all the important dates and communications, including the announcement of a webinar.

For more information and to apply, visit the [dedicated webpage](#), and for any question please email the MASTER Consortium through the dedicated email address [info\[@\]master-xr.eu](mailto:info[@]master-xr.eu). To stay up to date on the project's most important communications and events follow MASTER's [LinkedIn](#) page.

MASTER project is an EU-funded project under Horizon Europe programme, that focuses on utilizing Extended Reality (XR) technologies to enhance the teaching and training of robotics in manufacturing by developing an open XR platform. The project integrates key functionalities, creating safe and flexible robotic environments with advanced interaction mechanisms. By establishing an open platform for the creation and management of XR content in robotics, the project ultimately aims to benefit non-expert programmers to create robotic XR educational content.

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